

Figure S1. Specificity control of anti-glutamine staining of PDAC specimens. Cryostat sections (6 μm) of snap-frozen specimens from PDAC patients (all classified T3N1M0) were submitted to immunohistochemistry. Following an adapted crosslinking fixation protocol (see materials & methods), sections were probed with a rabbit Glutamine antibody (Abcam, ab9445) or a rabbit control antibody (Abcam, ab172730) at 1:100 dilution in *StainPerfect* antibody diluent and then further developed (see materials & methods). The result with two different PDAC specimens is shown.

Figure S2. MCT1 knock-down in T3M4 and A818-6 cells. T3M4 and A818-6 cells were transfected with either control siRNA or MCT1 siRNA for 24h and then further cultured under normal glutamine (Q10) or low glutamine supply (Q1) for 48h. A western blot figure from a representative experiment is shown.

Figure S3. NRF2 knockdown in T3M4 and A818-6 cells. T3M4 and A818-6 cells were transfected with either control siRNA or Nrf2 siRNA for 24h and then further cultured under normal glutamine (Q10) or low glutamine (Q1) supply for 48h. A western blot with nuclear extracts from a representative experiment is shown detecting Nrf2 (Abcam 62352, 1:500 in 5% BSA/TBST) using Lamin A/C (Santa Cruz, 1:1000 in 5% skimmed milk/TBST) as loading control.

Figure S4. Lactate protects T3M4 and A818-6 cells from glutamine depletion induced ROS stress
A) T3M4 and **B)** A818-6 cells were cultured under normal glutamine (Q10) or low glutamine (Q1) supply for 48h, either in the absence or presence of 1.5 mM glutathione (GSH) or 20 mM lactate given at the same period or 24h later. Then, cells were DCFDA-stained and analyzed by flow cytometry. Those fluorescence signals >10-fold greater than the background signal with unstained cells (dotted line) were quantified as percentage of highly ROS-stressed (ROS_{high}) cells (see figure 3).

Figure S5. Lactate protects PDAC cells from cell death and cell cycle arrest under glutamine shortage. A) T3M4 and B) A818-6 cells cultured with Q10 or Q1 for 48h in the absence or presence of 1.5 mM GSH or 20 mM lactate, added in parallel (48h) or 24h later, were collected and stained with PI and then analyzed by flow cytometry. The subG1 fraction containing apoptotic cells as well as G1, S- and G2/M-cell cycle phase fractions were gated as indicated for quantification (see figure 6).

Figure S6. T3M4 and A818-6 cells were treated with V9302 (2 μ M), CB839 (10 M) or DMSO for 48h either in the absence or presence of 20 mM lactate as indicated. Then, cells were DCFDA-stained and analyzed by flow cytometry. Those fluorescence signals >10-fold greater than the background signal with unstained cells (dotted line) were quantified as percentage of highly ROS-stressed (ROS_{high}) cells (see figure 8).

Figure S7. Lactate protects PDAC cells from V9302 or CB839 induced cell death and cell cycle arrest. T3M4 and A818-6 cells were treated with V9302 (2 μ M), CB839 (10 μ M) or DMSO for 48h either in the absence or presence of 20 mM lactate as indicated. Then, cells were collected, stained with PI and analysed by flow cytometry. The subG1 fraction containing apoptotic cells as well as G1, S- and G2/M-cell cycle phase fractions were gated as indicated for quantification (see figure 8).